

Is Smartphone a Tool for Learning Purpose in Dentistry? A Survey Among Students of Chatrapati Shahu Maharaj Shikshan Sanstha Dental College at Chatrapati Sambhajinagar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Smartphone and mobile internet usage among students has surged in recent years, highlighting their potential as educational tools.

Aim: The goal of this study is to analyse how dentistry students use smartphones for learning.

Material and method: A cross-sectional questionnaire was administered to dentistry undergraduate students at Chatrapati Shahu Maharaj Shikshan Sanstha(CSMSS) Dental College Chatrapati Sambhajinagar , Maharashtra. Data was gathered on smartphone and connection usage, general use, smartphone use for learning, and attitudes towards cell phones for learning. Descriptive statistics were calculated.

Results: Out of the 150 dental students, 148 students owned smartphones and were using social media. A total of 96% students agreed their smartphones helped them study more independently. Majority i.e. 96% of them used smartphones to access study material. Out of all the participants, i.e. 71% had apps related to dental education. Most of the students preferred their smartphones over library to access information and for research activities.

Conclusion: The attitude of the students was positive toward mobile learning, and majority of them expressed that smartphone usage for educational purposes should be encouraged by the college and staff. Social media positively impacted dentistry was the outcome of the study Therefore, this might present an opportunity for educators to design suitable teaching interventions and develop diverse learning approaches

Introduction:

Technology plays a crucial role in improving human well-being. Technological innovations were drawn on a route continual innovation. Such Innovation depicts the progression of phones to mobile phones. Finally, smartphones have become a vital aspect in our life and cannot ignore its importance. A smartphone. is a cellular phone with the capacity to run up to

date innovatory applications and surf the internet.¹ Smartphones have become widespread in the general population. Advanced mobile communications and portable calculations are now integrated in a mobile gadget known as "smartphone".²

The number of smartphone user in coming years is expected to be highest in India.³ Although 83% of adults between ages 18 and 29 own a smartphone mobile, mobile device ownership among college students is higher.⁴

Educational techniques must adapt to the changing context of society. Mobile gadgets, including smartphones and tablets are becoming more popular learning tools due to their portability and characteristics.⁵ Smartphones are no longer just used for communication, but also for academic purposes.⁶ Mobile learning (m-learning) enables students to study from anywhere and at any time.⁵

Students drive the adoption of new technology for learning, which is always developing, particularly with the emergence of mobile devices.⁷ Smartphones have utilized in educational activities to access course information.

Obtain information on pupils' performance, and to foster conversation and sharing among students' teachers. Mobile technology, including smartphones, can significantly enhance healthcare education.⁶ Research gaps exist on how students use cell phones for learning. This study assessed the use of smartphones for learning among dentistry students.

The study aimed to examine students' smartphone usage and attitudes towards using smartphones for learning purposes throughout time.

Material and method:

This cross sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted on dental students over a period of 3 months from May to July 2024 after obtaining permission from the ethical review board of the institution.

The questionnaire was tested for both face and content validity by a panel of experts to ensure comprehensive ability of dental students to be surveyed and no modifications were suggested. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed by conducting pilot study and it was found to be good. The questionnaire consisted of 11 items which included use of smartphones for learning purposes and assessment of student attitude towards smartphone for learning purposes. All the questions had binary responses to which participant had to select between Yes and No. Those students who were willing to participate and were present on the day of study were included in the study. The questionnaire was distributed among dental students from II year, III year, IV year and interns of Bachelor of Dental Surgery (BDS) after explaining in detail about the study. Student from all academic years were invited to complete the questionnaire in

their classroom after lecture. Participation in the study was voluntary. Each participant had taken a time of 5-6 min to fill the questionnaire.

Statistical analysis:

The survey being descriptive data was summarised as number and percentage. The data collected was then subjected to descriptive statistics.

Results:

A total of 150 dental student participated in the study out of which majority were female students i.e. 80.6% with average age of 22.31 years. Furthermore, most of the student were from final year i.e. 48% followed by interns i.e. 27% (table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of study sample by gender, age and year of studies

Variables	n (%)
Gender- Male Female	29 (19.3) 121 (80.7)
Age(years) Mean±SD	22.3±1.21
Year of study II year III year IV year Interns	20(13.3) 17 (11.3) 72 (48) 41 (27)

The study results revealed that maximum students used social media and social networking sites i.e. 96.4%. On the contrary dental applications were more significantly used by the final year and intern students in final year-90.24% and Interns-90.2%. Almost students from every class agreed that smartphone improved their access to courses and leaning material which was statistically significant ($p=0.0001$).

Table no.2:

Questionnaire	2 nd year n (%)	3 rd year n (%)	4 th year n (%)	Intern n (%)	Total n (%)	P value
Do you use social media and social networking sites? Yes No	19(95.0) 1(5.0)	17(100) 0(0)	72(100) 1(2.44)	40(97.6) 1(2.4)	167(96.4) 6(3.6)	0.0001
Does smartphone help you to study more independently? Yes No	20(100) 0(0)	17(100) 0(0)	70(97.2) 2(2.8)	38(92.7) 3(7.3)	135(96.4) 5(3.6)	0.0024
Do you prefer online lectures over classroom lecture? Yes No	15(75.0) 5(25.0)	3(17.6) 14(82.4)	27(37.5) 45(62.5)	27(65.8) 14(34.2)	87(51.7) 83(48.3)	0.0235
Do you have any apps related to dentistry? Yes No	11(55.0) 9(45.0)	12(70.6) 5(29.4)	37(90.2) 4(9.8)	50(90.2) 22(9.8)	121(71.4) 49(28.6)	0.0009
Do you think smartphone improve access to your courses and learning material? Yes No	20(100) 0(0)	16(94.1) 1(5.9)	38(98.6) 1(1.4)	38(92.7) 3(7.3)	132(96.4) 5(3.6)	0.0001
Smartphone usage should be encouraged and utilized more for learning purposes by the university and staff? Yes No	18(90.0) 2(10.0)	15(88.2) 2(11.6)	29(70.7) 12(29.3)	64(88.9) 8(11.1)	124(82.7) 26(17.3)	0.0045
Do you often prefer smartphone for research activities than using the library? Yes No	15(75.0) 5(25.0)	13(76.5) 4(23.5)	58(80.6) 14(19.4)	38(92.7) 3(7.3)	119(79.7) 31(20.3)	0.1125
Has smartphone helped you in learning clinical and laboratory procedure more precisely? Yes No	16(80.0) 4(20.0)	16(94.1) 1(5.9)	53(73.6) 19(26.4)	35(85.4) 6(14.6)	116(78) 31(22)	0.8512
Do you feel the need of social media to enhance your knowledge on current advances? Yes No	19(95.0) 1(5.0)	16(94.1) 1(5.9)	68(94.4) 4(5.6)	38(92.7) 3(7.3)	120(92.3) 10(7.7)	0.0421
Does social media helps you to overcome dental exam related						

stress and anxiety?						
Yes	12(60.0)	14(82.4)	22(53.7)	22(46.3)	80(63.5)	0.0873
No	8(40.0)	3(17.6)	19(46.3)	19(53.7)	47(36.5)	
Has social media positively impacted dentistry?						
Yes	19(95.0)	15(88.2)	38(92.7)	38(92.7)	125(91.)	0.0038
No	1(5.0)	2(11.8)	3(7.3)	3(7.3)	11(8.33)	

Interns have been using smartphones the most over library for research purposes followed by final year students for Interns it was 92.68% and Final year it was 80.56%. (table-2) Students in almost large number from every section agreed that smartphone has helped them in learning clinical and laboratory procedure more precisely with help of online demonstration videos. Majority of students agreed that social media is important for enhancing knowledge and current advances globally which was statistically significant ($p=0.0421$). Social media has positively impacted dentistry was accepted by almost majority students of every class. (table-2)

Discussion:

Smartphones have become a crucial part of students everyday life. According to present study mobile is the most widely used device i.e. 100% of adult between 18-29 age group own a smartphone and around 97% used social media which is similar to previous study conducted by Sen et al.⁸ and Chennupati⁹ et al. among dental students in which 100% of student won smartphones.

Another study conducted by Makkar et al. in 2015¹⁰, Kumar et al. in 2015¹¹ and Deogade et al. in 2017¹² reported that 100% of dental student had smartphone and social media while this present study reported 96.43% students agreeing that smartphone have help them study more independently and the same have agreed that it improve their access to courses and learning material.

In the current time scenario globally people and majorly students are shifting towards digital education. Even dental institute are used in social media application as a source for digital learning helping students with their seminars, presentations and lectures more precisely. In our study it showed that around 71% students had dentistry related application for knowledge purpose compared to 37.3% in a study conducted by Rung et al. in 2014¹³. This study also showed that most students i.e. 79.7% preferred to use smartphone over library for research purposes and the result were similar to study by Storie D et al.¹⁴ in 2014 conducted on medical students. According to our study around 92% participants felt the need of social media for enhancing knowledge on current advances while it was 51.4% in similar study by Sen et al.⁸ in 2016.

In the current time scenario globally people and majorly students are shifting towards digital education. Even dental institute are used in social media application as a source for digital learning helping students with their seminars, presentations and lectures more precisely. This broad spectrum of social media has ability to cover, interact and develop. Smartphones has acquired a special room in students' day to day life. The increase rate of impact that advanced technology is having on students responded in modern effective means of delivery more characteristics quality education.

The strength of our study is that we have taken a variety of sample from different classes and budding dentists opinion have been recorded on smartphone use in pre-clinical as well as clinical study. The limitation of present study is that it includes a small sample size, and the survey was done in one single dental college therefore, generalisation should be done with caution.

Conclusion: The attitude of the students was positive toward smartphone learning and majority of them expressed that smartphone helped them study independently. Social media positively impacted dentistry was the outcome of the study therefore, this might present an opportunity for educators to design suitable teaching interventions and develop diverse learning approaches

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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